

Zitterbewegung in a Statistical Mechanical Gas?

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In a series of notes [2]-[9], a linear 2x2 matrix equation was developed for Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2=p^2+m^2$ (1). This was done by noting that $p/E=\cos(a)=\cos^2(a/2)-\sin^2(a/2)$ and $m/E=\sin(a)=2\sin(a/2)\cos(a/2)$. It was noted that the positive energy eigenvector is $1/\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ with $c=1$. The resulting theory appeared to be of a quantum mechanical nature with probabilities of $.5(1+v)$ and $.5(1-v)$ for a particle to move forward and backward while moving on average along the x axis with speed v. Knuth [18] has also proposed a similar statistical model. The 2x2 matrix model reproduces Schrodinger's zitterbewegung. [1] It was also shown [21] that the probabilities $f_1=.5(1+v)$ and $f_2=.5(1-v)$ result from maximizing entropy subject to the constraint $(f_1-f_2)=v$. This seems to link the statistics of quantum mechanics with that of regular statistical mechanics. It was also shown that f_1 and f_2 were consistent with the relativistic statistical mechanics of Kaniadakis [20]. In this note, we wish to investigate whether a 2x2 matrix model can be developed for particles with two allowable energy states e_1 and e_2 . Particles under these conditions are already described by statistical mechanics, but the 2x2 model seems to suggest that it might be possible to describe them also in a 2x2 quantum mechanical matrix approach. If this can be done, then it might be possible to have zitterbewegung for the constraint matrix just as there is zitterbewegung for the velocity matrix in the 2x2 matrix model for the energy momentum equation. Here, zitterbewegung would imply that there are fluctuations about the energy per particle of the system E/N , possibly with a periodicity. The constraint matrix here is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Statistical Mechanics for 2 energy level system

Consider only two allowable energy levels for particles in a box, namely e_1 and e_2 and probabilities f_1 and f_2 . Then:

$f_1+f_2=1$ and $e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 = E/N$ where E is the total energy and N the total number of particles.

This problem can be solved to give:

$$f_1 = [(E/N) - e_2]/[e_1 - e_2] \quad \text{and} \quad f_2 = [E - e_1]/[e_2 - e_1] \quad (2)$$

It is interesting to compare this with the result from statistical mechanics using the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, namely

$f_1 = C \exp(-e_1/T)$ and $f_2 = C \exp(-e_2/T)$ where C is the normalization constant and T the temperature which needs to be determined.

One can solve for T as:

$$T = (e_2 - e_1) / \{ \ln[(E/N - e_2)/(e_1 - E/N)] \}$$

This is of exactly the same form as the constraint used for the 2x2 matrix model of the energy-momentum equation. There:

constraint = $.5 \ln[(1-v)/(1+v)]$ Here, v takes the place of E/N and -1 and $+1$ the place of e_1 and e_2 .

If one solves for $f_2 = \exp(-e_2/T) / \{ \exp(-e_1/T) + \exp(-e_2/T) \}$ one obtains:

$$f_2 = [E - e_1] / [e_2 - e_1]$$

As an aside, in general $\sum f_i = 1$ and $\sum e_i f_i = E/N$ where one sums on the i 's. These are equivalent to $\sum (e_i - E/N) f_i = 0$

One can show that $f_i = \exp(-e_i/T) / \sum \exp(-e_i/T)$ is a solution of the two above equations.

To do so, one can note that: $-d/d(1/T) \sum \exp(-e_i/T) = \sum e_i f_i = (E/N) \sum \exp(-e_i/T)$

It should be noted that for the case of e_1 and e_2 , we do not need to use the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution to solve the problem. Kaniadakis [20] has supplied a different distribution. One can try to solve for T with his distribution:

$$F_i = (\sqrt{1 + k^2/T^2 e_i^2} + k/T e_i)^{-1/k}$$

In the e_1, e_2 case, all we need is the result (2), which is not dependent on the distribution model which carries a parameter T (temperature).

2x2 Matrix Approach

In the e_1, e_2 statistical mechanics approach we consider here, there is no energy-momentum equation as a starting point. In notes [2]-[9], however, it was shown that one does not need (1)

as a starting point. Rather, one needs a matrix which will convert an eigenvector of (1,0) into the full eigenvector (sqrt(f1), sqrt(f2)).

For the statistical mechanical problem the constraint matrix E is
$$\begin{bmatrix} |e_1 & 0| \\ |0 & e_2| \end{bmatrix}$$

We already know f1 and f2 from the previous section, so we can take sqrt(f1) and sqrt(f2) to create an eigenvector. We can also call this eigenvector (cos(a/2), sin(a/2)).

Let us postulate a matrix like that used in [2]-[9] namely:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(a) & \sin(a) \\ \sin(a) & -\cos(a) \end{bmatrix} = H/w \quad (3)$$

In the case of the energy momentum linear 2x2 matrix, w was the

eigenvalue, namely E, the energy of the particle. Here, there is no equation to use as a starting point, so this raises the question as to the value of w. If one examines, cos(a) and sin(a), one sees that they are divided by |e1-e2|. In the energy momentum case, cos(a)=p/E and sin(a)=m/E, so perhaps |e1-e2| can be taken for w. Equivalently, e2-e1=E/N-e1.

The matrix in (3) will act as an evolution operator on (1,0) and (0,1) which are the eigenvalues of the constraint matrix E converting them into (cos(a/2), sin(a/2)) or (sqrt(f1), sqrt(f2)). (In [2]-[9], these same eigenvectors were those of the V matrix which was the constraint matrix in that case.)

Then one can evaluate:

$$\begin{aligned} E(t) &= \exp(iHt) E \exp(-iHt) \\ &= \cos^2(|e_1-e_2|t) \begin{bmatrix} |e_1 & 0| \\ |0 & e_2| \end{bmatrix} + i \cos(|e_1-e_2|t) \sin(|e_1-e_2|t) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (e_2-e_1)\sin(a) \\ (e_1-e_2)\sin(a) & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \\ &\quad \sin^2(|e_1-e_2|t) \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(a)e_1 + \sin^2(a)e_2 & \cos(a)\sin(a)(e_1-e_2) \\ \cos(a)\sin(a)(e_1-e_2) & \sin^2(a)e_1 + \cos^2(a)e_2 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

with: $\cos^2(a) = \frac{(E-e_2) + (E-e_1)}{(e_1-e_2)}$ and $\sin^2(a) = -2 \sqrt{\frac{(E-e_1)(E-e_2)}{(e_1-e_2)}}$

It appears that there is zitterbewegung which seems to suggest fluctuations in E/N which are of a periodic nature. It also appears that the zitterbewegung represents a quantum mechanical type description, at least to a certain degree, of the statistical mechanical problem of particles moving in a box. It is not clear what the imaginary portion of E(t) means. In the case of the velocity matrix V(t) for the 2x2 model of the momentum energy equation in one dimension, the imaginary part was considered to be motion perpendicular to the one dimension. In quantum mechanics an imaginary portion of energy usually is associated with decay. Perhaps, here it plays a similar role. In the case of V(t) it is believed that the periodicity is related to physical

motion, so here zitterbewegung would imply physical periodicity in the average energy of a particle in a hot gas. It is almost as if the periodicity were an energy oscillation of sorts, but in a statistical mechanical system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a 2x2 matrix equation, linear in E and similar to the Dirac equation, was proposed in [2]-[9] for the energy momentum equation (1). This allowed one to solve (1) and obtain an eigenvector of $1/\sqrt{2} (\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ with $c=1$. It is believed that $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ are probabilities of this quantum mechanical type solution. It was also found that $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ could be obtained from maximizing entropy subject to $(f_1-f_2)=v$. Thus, there seems to be an equivalency between quantum mechanical statistics and regular statistical mechanics for this model. In addition, the model reproduces Schrodinger zitterbewegung. In this note, a 2x2 matrix model is proposed for a system of particles in a box with allowable energies of e_1 and e_2 . This system can be described by statistical mechanics, but the purpose of the note is to see if it can also be described in quantum mechanical terms. Doing so seems to give zitterbewegung results for a matrix $\begin{vmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{vmatrix}$ suggesting that there may be periodic time

dependent fluctuations in a statistical mechanical gas. It is possible that this zitterbewegung may be associated with a kind of oscillation in the hot gas. The expectation of the above matrix is E/N where E is the total energy of the gas and N the number of particles.

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